

Co-relation of Blood in Urine with Likeness of Teaching as Profession

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ABSTRACT

Teaching is a profession that gives rise to all types of professions. Profession means that someone had complete knowledge about a specific field like doctor, engineer, accountant and lawyer. Goal of this study was to link likeness of teaching as profession with presence of blood in urine. Sum of 89 students participated in this study. Urine analysis of all these subjects was performed by urine dipstick test. The existence of red blood cells in urine is known as hematuria and it is of two types. First one is that which shows the symptoms of brown coloration of urine. 11.76% males had blood in urine and 88.24% had no blood in urine while 18.37% females had blood in urine and 81.63% had no blood in urine. 50% males and 14.29% females had blood in urine while 50% males and 85.71% females had no blood in urine. End result of this study was that presence or absence of blood in urine had no co-relation with likeness of teaching as profession.

Keywords: Teaching likeness as profession, RBCs in urine.

1. Introduction

The existence of red blood cells in urine called as hematuria and it is of two types. First one is that which shows the symptoms of brown coloration of urine. The second one is invisible through human eye and known as microscopic hematuria. In this type color of urine did not change so it can be detected accidentally or by using microscope. Reasons of this type of hematuria can be different, either it can arise from filtration system of kidney (into the glomerular) or it can arise from kidney (outside of the glomerular).

Blood can be leaked into urine by kidney parts and parts of urinary tract. Any type of the injury into the glomeruli can cause the red blood cells to leak into the urine. The main reason of hematuria is infections of urinary tract like kidney stones. When certain bacteria get entered into by urethra and multiplied in the bladder. It causes pain and very smelling urine and burning with it. Almost anyone can have RBCs in urine including children and teens. Men having age more than 50 had regular hematuria because of larger prostate glands.

Teaching is a profession that gives rise to all types of professions. Profession means that someone had complete knowledge about a specific field like doctor, engineer, accountant and lawyer. All of these are considered as profession which means profiteer. It is also considered as occupation (a way to earn money).

Teaching plays key role in preparing students to make them professionals and to prepare them to play constructive role in building of a nation and country. Teacher develops the knowledge as well as ethics of each student. He should know about the strengths and the weak pointes of his every student and he should polish their capabilities. He must have to focus on moral values of his pupils. He should behave the same as he asked his students to behave. His personality, hard work and behavior should motivate the students.

Goal of this study is to link likeness of teaching as profession with presence of blood in urine.

The scientific workers have already been co-relate different parameters of a specific topic (1-10).

2. Method and Material

Sum of 89 students participated in this study. Urine analysis of all these subjects was performed by urine dipstick test. Blood in urine was checked.

2.1. Study Design

Questionnaire was designed and questions were asked about the occurrence of blood in urine. Likeness and dis-likeness of students about teaching as profession was estimated.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

Mathematical analysis was done by using MS Excel.

3. Results and Discussion

Co-relation of blood in urine with likeness of teaching as profession is given in table 1. 66 students like teaching as a profession. From that 66 students 11.76% males had blood in urine and 88.24% had no blood in urine while 18.37% females had blood in urine and 81.63% had no blood in urine. 23 students did not like teaching as job. From that 23 subjects 50% males and 14.29% females had blood in urine while 50% males and 85.71% females had no blood in urine.

Table 1. Co-relation of blood in urine with likeness of teaching as profession

Gender	Likeness of teaching as profession		Dis-likeness of teaching as profession	
	Blood in urine present	Blood in urine absent	Blood in urine present	Blood in urine absent
Males	11.76%	88.24%	50%	50%
Females	18.37%	81.63%	14.29%	85.71%

Research based project had given important results in this study.

4. Conclusion

End result of this study was that presence or absence of blood in urine had no co-relation with likeness of teaching as profession.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, and personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

Authors declare that they consented for the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

Authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to data collection, research, and paper drafting.

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